

Effects of silica level on whitebacked planthopper

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Survival of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) nymphs on rice seedlings growing in culture solution with three silica (SiO₂) levels was examined.

from 5.5 to 6.0. Each silica level was replicated five times.

When plants were 15 and 30 days old, 10 first-instar nymphs were introduced in each cage.

On plants treated with silica, very few nymphs developed into adults (Table 1). At 15 days after infestation, the highest number of adults was recorded on plants with no silica.

For population buildup counts, 5 pairs of 3- to 5-day-old WBPH adults

were introduced in each cage. Surviving adults were counted 5 days after caging. Progeny were counted when plants were 35 days old.

The number of nymphs was highest at 0 ppm SiO₂ and lowest at 150 ppm (Table 2). The number of males increased as silica concentration increased.

Apparently SiO₂ induces development of males but inhibits feeding of WBPH. ■

Table 1. Effect of silica on survival of whitebacked planthoppers^a at IRRI.

SiO ₂ (ppm) in culture solution	Av no. leaves/plant	Surviving whitebacked planthoppers ^b (no.)								
		10 DAI		15 DAI		20 DAI		25 DAI		
		N	A	N	A	N	A	N	A	NG
0	6.8 a	8.6 a	1.4 a	5.4 a	4.2 a	0.0 b	9.2 a	0.0 a	9.2 a	53.0 a
50	5.2 b	8.0 a	0.2 b	5.4 a	2.2 b	0.0 b	7.0 b	0.0 a	7.0 b	0.0 b
100	4.2 b	6.6 b	0.0 b	5.0 a	1.8 b	0.4 ab	5.8 c	0.0 a	6.2 b	0.0 b
150	4.2 b	6.4 b	0.0 b	4.6 a	1.2 b	0.8 a	5.0 c	0.0 a	5.8 b	0.0 b

^a Av of 5 replications. Separation of means in a column and under each level by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^bDAI = days after infestation, N = nymphs, A = adults, NG = new generation.

One 10-day-old seedling of variety N22 (*Wbph* 1 gene for resistance to WBPH) was transplanted to each pot containing a culture solution. Each pot was put in a cage. A 60-liter culture solution contained 100 ml N, 100 ml P, 100 ml K, 100 ml Ca, 100 ml Mg, 10 ml microelements, 60 ml Fe EDTA. Graded levels of silica as sodium metasilicate (Na₂SiO₃5H₂) were added to the culture solution and the pH adjusted

Table 2. Population buildup of whitebacked planthopper on N22 rice variety grown with different levels of SiO₂ at IRRI.^a

SiO ₂ (ppm) in culture solution	Leaves (no.)	Mortality (%) 5 DAI	25 DAI			
			Nymphs (no.)	Males (no.)	Females (no.)	Total
0	1.2 a	16.0 a	188.2 a	35.6 c	25.4 a	249.2 a
50	4.2 b	36.0 a	100.6 ab	42.4 bc	21.8 b	164.8 ab
100	4.4 b	24.0 a	91.8 b	52.6 ab	17.4 c	167.8 abc
150	4.4 b	28.0 a	61.4 b	53.8 a	18.2 c	133.4 bc

^aAv of 5 replications. Separation of means in a column under each level by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. DAI = days after infestation.

Disruption of striped rice borer males' orientation to pheromone traps

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Disruption of male striped rice borer (*Chilo suppressalis*) orientation to monitoring traps by a single spray application of pheromone was investigated in paddy fields in 1981. Microencapsulated pheromone formulation as a mixture of (z)-11-hexadecenal and (z)-13-octadecenal at 4.5:1 was prepared by urea (1) formalin (2) copolymerization, mixed with a spreader, and sprayed at 10 mg and 30 mg on weeds of paddy

Disruption by microencapsulated pheromone of male striped borer moth orientation to monitoring hap.^a Korea, 1981.

Time after pheromone application (days)	Males trapped (no.)					
	10 mg		30 mg ^b			
	Treated	Not treated	Treated	Not treated	Treated	Not treated
Before treatment	5	19	9	11	23	19
1	0	4	0	2	0	6
2	0	1	0	1	0	8
3	1	1	0	2	0	6
4	0	0	0	1	0	10
5	1	0	0	1	0	7
6	0	1	0	1	0	2
7	0	0	0	1	0	3
8	1	0	2	3	0	4
9	1	1	0	2	0	1
10	1	1	0	2	0	2
11	0	0	0	0	1	4
12	0	1	3	4	1	0
13	0	0	2	2	0	1
14	0	2	3	3	3	3
Total trapped	5	12	10	25	5	57

^aTrap baited with 100 μg pheromone as the attractant source. ^b30 mg applications in two different areas.

bank around a monitoring trap containing 100 µg attractant.

Males caught were counted daily

from 10 days before application to 15 days after. The ability of male moths to locate the trap source was suppressed at

30 mg for 7-10 days (see table). The pheromone had lost much of its disruptive effect 10 days after application. ■

Soil and crop management

Nitrogen management in flooded rice

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A field experiment on flooded rice in the 1981 monsoon season evaluated urea briquet placement (5 cm below soil surface), margosa seedcake-coated urea, shellac-coated urea, sulfur-coated urea, farmyard manure (FYM) + urea, and urea split application. Experimental field soil was silty clay loam (Mollisol). Each nitrogen source was applied at 60 kg N/ha.

There was no yield advantage in 3 split applications of urea over 2 splits at 60 kg N/ha (see table). Margosa seedcake-coated urea and shellac-coated urea also did not offer any significant improvement in yield over urea applied in three split doses. Urea + FYM was equal to urea alone (3 splits).

Sulfur-coated urea produced significantly higher yields than did ordinary urea applied in three split doses. Urea briquet placement 1 week after trans-

Yield of rough rice at 60 kg N/ha.^a

Nitrogen source	Method and time of application	Grain yield (t/ha)	N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
None	—	3.32	—
Urea	Broadcast, 3 splits	3.98	11
Urea	Broadcast, 2 splits (transplanting and tiller initiation)	4.21	15
Urea	Broadcast, 2 splits (tiller initiation and panicle initiation)	4.24	15
Urea briquet	Placement at 5 cm, 1 wk after transplanting	4.85	25
Urea briquet	Placement at 5 cm, 3 wk after transplanting	5.37	34
Margosa seedcake-coated urea	Broadcast at transplanting	3.98	11
Margosa seedcake-coated urea	Broadcast 2 splits (transplanting and tiller initiation)	3.81	8
Shellac-coated urea	Broadcast at transplanting	4.24	15
Sulfur-coated urea	Broadcast at transplanting	4.43	18
FYM + urea (30 + 30)	Broadcast and mixed in soil before transplanting	3.64	5
FYM + urea (30 + 30)	FYM mixed with soil before transplanting and urea broadcast 3 wk after transplanting	3.99	11
S.Em ±		0.15	—
C.D. 5%		0.45	—

^aFYM = farmyard manure.

planting was also significantly superior to ordinary urea (2 or 3 splits), but gave lower yields than placement 3 weeks after transplanting — probably because of the relatively long growth period (144 days) of the rice variety (Jaya) grown.

The highest yield was with urea briquet placement 3 weeks after transplanting.

Nitrogen use efficiency with urea briquet was more than 2 times as high as 2 or 3 split applications of ordinary urea. ■

Algae in rice fields of Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, India

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Samples of algae were collected during October and November 1981 (monsoon season). Rainfall during the period was 370.9 mm, maximum temperature range was 39.0°-25.5° C, and minimum temperature range was 24.5°-16.5° C. Standing water of 1-2 cm was maintained in the fields by lift irrigation from an open well.

Abundance of nitrogen-fixing algae (Cyanophyta species). Tamil Nadu, India.

Species	Relative abundance ^a
<i>Gloeocapsa decorticans</i>	x
<i>Anabaena oryzae</i>	xx
<i>Cylindrospermum muscicola</i>	x
<i>Nostoc sphaericum</i>	x
<i>Aulosira prolifica</i>	x
<i>Calothrix</i> sp.	

^ax = rare, xx = moderate.

Species of algae identified consisted of 11 Cyanophyta, 6 Chlorophyta, 2 Euglenophyta, and 5 Bacillariophyta. Of the 11 Cyanophyta species, 6 are known to be nitrogen-fixing algae (see table). ■

Effect of seedling age on susceptibility to aluminum toxicity

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Although aluminum toxicity is rarely a problem in wetland rice, it may impair growth even in flooded soils when soil pH remains low because of strong acidity and low microbial activity. Relatively young seedlings may fail to establish on some acid sulfate soils.

Solution culture technique was used to examine the effect of seedling age on